

METHODOLOGY FOR WORKING ON THE OPEN AIR IN FINE ART CLASSES

Baymetov Botir Boltabayevich

Professor of Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Khamrakulova Mukaddam Tojikozi kizi

Doctoral student of Chirchik State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12295857>

Abstract: In fine arts lessons, students learned about the history of the origins of the landscape genre, its development, the artists who created it, as well as their creativity. At the same time, thoughts were expressed about the unique aspects of painting in the heart of nature.

Key words: Awakening period, household style, historical genre, battalion genre, landscape style, imagination, artist, genre, plener, nature, composition, artist, mountain view, monumental building.

INTRODUCTION

In the landscape genre, the artist's emotions, thoughts and dreams are expressed through real or imagined scenes of nature. This genre depicts natural landscapes, architectural structures, mountain landscapes and sea waves that change as a result of human activity. Scenes of nature are used as a means of supplementing the content of thematic compositions; they are widely used in paintings and graphic works, and sculpture reliefs. The reflection of natural landscapes has attracted the attention of artists since ancient times. Scenes of nature and its elements are widely found in paintings made in various everyday, historical and battle genres. The depiction of the beauty of nature and the reflection of existence is characteristic of the landscape genre. There is hardly an artist he doesn't like. Because a person who loves life always feels in his heart that he is a child of nature. Enjoys the beauty of the environment. In order to turn a natural view that has attracted the attention of an artist into a work of art, you need to think about it artistically, create it in your mind as a work and reflect it on fabric. Some works of the landscape genre directly depict a real view of nature, others are creatively presented in the imagination. Sometimes these two cases can be in the same work. The emergence of the landscape genre is rooted in distant history. For example, a tomb painting at Beni-Hassan from the 1st century BC depicts a hunt for a wild mouse. This genre appeared independently in China in the 6th century. In European art of the Renaissance, it was formed on a scientific basis, that is, on the basis of linear and airy (color) perspective.

LITERARY ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Landscape arose as an independent genre on a large scale. A new stage in the landscape genre began in the second half of the 9th century. The attempt to create works full of light and air, truthfully depicting natural scenes, occupied a significant place in the work of French artists. Since the end of the 9th century, it has become common to paint in the open air. Artists such as J. Constable in Great Britain and A. Ivanov in Russia were active in this regard. Little by little, representatives of the Barbizon school in France, as well as K. Korot, seriously took up this issue and contributed to its development. In the works of artists, the genre of landscape has become a means of expressing the waves of the human heart, as well as the appearance of ordinary nature. Gradually, in the landscapes of artists, the concrete human image began to be perceived as an integral part of nature, and not as an expression of individual character. Admiration for the artistic and aesthetic beauty of plein air painting became more and more intense, and the main artistic image was considered to be a second of views in different seasonal spaces. The

real development of plein air painting coincided with the second half of the 19th century, and from this period the word “plein air” came into use, came into circulation and began to be applied to the works of the French impressionists. artists C. Monet, C. Pissarro, O. Renoir. From the late 19th century to the early 20th century, plein air painting found expression in the work of European, Asian and American artists.

RESULTS

Through imagination, the artist introduces many innovations into the world of artistic image in comparison with historical or modern schools and directions of image. Their originality was manifested in the realistic depiction of urban scenes, they were able to harmoniously describe scenes of nature, the rainbow of city life, the color rhythm of people, buildings, the environment, air and trees, combined with various situations that form a symphony. movements. They sought to achieve light absorption by juxtaposing colors while maintaining their pure power. In everything depicted, they moved on to depicting the situation of burial under the rays of the sun. Spectators were amazed by the rhythm of the city and the humidity of the air, the restless movement of clouds in the sky. These artists observe the “breathing” of a day or a scene from different times and capture the corresponding experiences on fabric. In the artist’s canvas, the main place is occupied by the experiences received from reality, and not its materiality. This painting came to Uzbekistan at the end of the 19th century. Urol Tansikboev, a skilled master of the landscape genre, devoted his entire life and career to depicting the nature of Uzbekistan. Urol Tansikboev is a great artist who made a great contribution to the development of fine arts, artistically depicting the nature of our beautiful country. Urol Tansikboev vividly expressed in his landscape works the complex of colors characteristic of our nature. In particular, his work “Spring” (1947) artistically depicts a natural landscape covered in various colors. His landscapes very skillfully depict open spaces, and with great skill the subtle and graceful secrets of this space are displayed. The artist's works attract attention because they show width and colors, they are clearly expressed and these colors are proportional to each other. The masters of the landscape genre created in their works a generalized image of their beloved country, embodying in them the fantasy of a creative person who changes nature according to his will. Landscape paintings by O. Tansikboev convey the beauty and grandeur of nature. The artist painted the charming landscapes of the country using a complex planned composition, an elegant and colorful palette of colors, and sometimes decorative contrasts. In his lyrical landscapes and epic canvases, the beauty of the Motherland is glorified with passionate feeling. The artist lovingly depicted valleys with flowers, endless deserts and quiet bodies of water in the mountains.

DISCUSSION

The best works of Uzbek artists of this period attract attention with their unique style, expressiveness of images, and high professional skill. Although these works are not similar to each other in style and theme, they are in harmony with each other thanks to the common idea, an impressive reflection of modern reality, a clear description of the inner world, attitude to work and way of life of the Uzbek people. Any artist working in the landscape genre tries to clearly present the idea that he wants to promote, reflecting through his imagination and life view important events and phenomena in the life of society. It also shows the distance, aspect ratio, and color relationships between objects in the scene. Although the landscape genre is somewhat complex, the artist can express it through fantastic fantasy. At the same time, he tries

to correctly describe the characteristics of things, the proportions of parts and direction. When creating an image, the artist imagines drawing a tree along with clouds in the sky, a shore of water or a lake, a bridge, nature from above and tries to mentally imprint the compositional sc

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that nature teaches the artist a lot and reveals the essence of the surrounding things. Therefore, today's artist should create more works in the lap of nature. Then you can create works of art that touch the hearts of everyone.ene on the fabric.

References:

1. Abdirasilov S., Tolipov N., Oripova N. Rangtasvir.Toshkent. O'zbekiston, 2006.
2. Abdirasilov S. Tasviriy san'at va uni o'qitish metodikasi. Toshkent. Ilm Ziyo nashriyoti, 2011.
3. Abdirasilov S., Boymetov B., Tolipov N. Tasviriy san'at. – T.: Ilm Ziyo nashriyoti, 2010.
4. Abdurahmonov G'. Kompozitsiya. -T.,TDPU, 2009
5. Boymetov B.B. Pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasalarida talabalarga kompozitsiya fanini o'qitishning nazariyasi va amaliyoti. "Science and Education" Scientific Journal. -Uzbekistan: 2020. №7.
6. Boymetov B.B., Nurtaev O'.N. Tasviriy san'at texnologiyasi va nusxa ko'chirish (Oliy o'quv yurtlari uchun o'quv qo'llanma). -T.: Iqtisod-moliya, 2007
7. Boymetov B.B. Qalamtasvir. -T.: Ilm ziyo, 2007
8. Hasanov R., Tasviriy san'at asoslari.-T., G'ofur G'ulom. 2009 y.